

On the Study of a Simple Method of Separation of Carrier-free RaE from RaD

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A simple and convenient procedure in separating carrier-free RaE from RaD has been developed. The principle involves in the addition of ammonium acetate to the carrier-free solution of RaD in equilibrium with RaE, thereby raising the pH above 6.8. The solution is passed through a column of glass powder where most of the daughter is adsorbed and nearly all of RaD passes away on washing with water. RaE adsorbed on glass powder is then eluted by hot concentrated nitric acid. The daughter activity is of very high radiochemical purity. In this process 3% of the daughter activity is retained by glass surface. On introducing a correction factor of 3%, a complete quantitative separation can be achieved. The method is also successful in presence of excess of lead. Too much of ammonium acetate has a deterioration effect on the extent of adsorption of RaE on glass powder.

Most of the methods, described in literature, for the separation of RaE from RaD are based on the deposition of RaE on metallic foils¹⁻³, preferably in a reducing atmosphere. Although advantageous in physical studies, its subsequent operations are necessary to obtain the product in a purely carrier-free state. In target reactions, if lead metal is taken as a starting material, nitric acid is the best solvent after bombardment which brings in an oxidising atmosphere, unfavourable for the deposition by reduction. In view of these difficulties, recent advances in chromatography³⁻⁶, ion exchange⁷, and other techniques have been undertaken by various workers. A carrier-free product, free from traces of foreign substances, for radiochemical study with good reproducibility has, however, still remained a problem. An attempt has therefore been made to separate completely RaE, which is in equilibrium with RaD, without any carrier or any traces of foreign substances.

Lead is expected to form mainly a cationic complex like $(PbAc)^+$ with ammonium acetate, whereas bismuth in tracer concentration forms hydrolytic products when acidity is reduced to a considerable extent by addition of ammonium acetate to the mineral acid solution of the lead and of bismuth in tracer concentration. The adhering property of hydrolytic products⁸⁻¹⁰ of bismuth on glass surface and its subsequent elution with nitric acid has been utilised as a method of separation of RaE from RaD.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Carrier-free RaD in equilibrium with RaE was supplied by Messrs Philips Duphar and all other reagents used were of analytical reagent quality. The activity was measured by using a liquid G. M. counter. A typical experiment is described below.

RaD in equilibrium with RaE in dilute nitric acid solution was first neutralised with

FIG. 1.

- A. Column containing glass powder (120 mesh)
- B. Jacket.
- C. Collecting vessel.

ammonia, using methyl orange as indicator, and just made acidic once again using 1:1 HNO_3 . To this solution an ammonium acetate solution (10 ml, containing α . 1.5 g.) was added to neutralise the free mineral acid. The pH was between 6.6 and 7.0. The solution was heated for sometime and passed through the glass column (shown in Fig. 1), packed with powdered glass wool (120 mesh). It contained 12 g. of glass powder in 24 cm, having an internal diameter of 1 cm. The column had an outside jacket through which steam could be circulated to keep it hot during adsorption as well as elution. The solution was allowed to drop at the rate of 0.3 to 0.4 ml/min. The drops were collected in a conical flask which was connected to a water pump for regulating the flow. The column was washed with distilled water (30 ml). Test for bismuth was made in the collecting vessel. Bismuth was found to remain adsorbed on the glass column and whole

of lead was found in the collecting vessel. Bismuth was then eluted by pouring HNO_3 (conc.). It was found convenient to pour the acid approximately 15 ml in one instalment and stop the downward flow. It was kept hot by circulating steam through the external jacket for about an hour. HNO_3 was taken out and the column was washed with HNO_3 (conc., 40-50 ml) in several instalments. On examination it was found that 97% of bismuth could be eluted. The product was found to be of very high radiochemical purity. The results are recorded in Table I.

DISCUSSION

Lima and Abro¹¹ described an elaborate procedure for radiochemical separation of lead and bismuth, using EDTA. Though the method is rapid, the recovery and purity are not very satisfactory when both the mother and daughter are in tracer level.

Sato *et al.*¹² in electro-chromatographic separation of these products also preferred addition of some inactive components of isotopic substances to harness the relative speed of migration. Dedek⁷ in the application of ion-exchange resins in the separation of lead and bismuth and subsequent elution with HCl could not guarantee any success in presence of macro amounts of lead. Conte *et al.*¹³ recently investigated the deposition on nickel plate at steam temperature and the subsequent removal of nickel through descending and ascending chromatography. This procedure involves a number of steps.

TABLE I

Vol. of soln. taken = 10 ml.

AmAc added.	pH.	Inactive Pb added as its nitrate.	%RaE		%RaD or amount of inactive lead (1×10^{-6} g. adhering to RaE.	Remarks.
			Adsorbed.	Eluted.		
Group A.						
1.5 g.	6.6-7.0		99.87	98.60		(a) Deteriorating effect on adsorption caused by too much excess of AmAc.
1.5	6.6-7.0		99.93	95.90		
5.0	6.8-7.0		77.09 (a)	95.03 (b)		
10.0	6.8-7.0		40.41	98.84		(b) $96.32 + 3 = 99.32\%$
			Av. 96.32			
Group B.						
1.5	6.6-7.0		99.91	97.12		
1.5	6.6-7.0		99.47	96.81		
1.5	6.6-7.0		99.93	97.70		$97.21 + 3 = 100.21\%$
			Av. 99.77	Av. 97.21		
Group C.						
1.5	6.6-7.0	0.1990 g.	..	95.90	50 (ca.)	
1.5	6.6-7.0	0.3920	..	96.94	50 "	
1.5	6.6-7.0	1.0564	..	96.92	100 "	$96.53 + 3 = 99.55\%$
1.5	6.6-7.0	1.3557	..	96.44	100	
			Av. 96.55			
Group D.						
..	..	..	..	0.14		An addition of 3% to the recovery (vide A, B, C) makes the separation perfectly quantitative. Radiochemical purity is always above 99.7%.
..	..	..	..	0.17		
..	..	..	..	0.35		
..	..	..	..	0.26		
..	..	..	..	Av. 0.23		

N.B. In all the experiments 2000-3000 counts/min. of activity in 10 ml was taken. Group A refers to separation where the daughter and mother are in equilibrium. Group B includes the study with pure RaE free from its mother. Group C includes the study with pure RaE in presence of finite amounts of inactive lead. Group D refers to the purity of RaE when separated from its mother in secular equilibrium.

Incidentally, the process, which has been developed by complexing RaD with ammonium acetate and raising the pH favourable for the adsorption of RaE, is simple and free from any complexities.

12. *Anal Chem.*, 1956, **27**, 521.13. *J. Chromatog.*, 1960, **3**, 96.

The results recorded in Table I justify the success of the procedure. In group A where RaE is in equilibrium with RaD, too much excess of ammonium acetate reduces the extent of adsorption of RaE on glass surface. This is probably due to the formation of an anionic complex of bismuth. Results in A series refers to a correction at zero time. In order to avoid this correction factor for the successful separation, we separated RaE in the procedure already described. Data in group B refer to the study with RaE free from RaD, where the extent of adsorption and elution can be studied without taking any correction factor as regards the growth of RaE from RaD after separation. The extent of adsorption was studied after passing the solution through the column. The solution with its washings was collected, acidified, and bismuth added; the solution thus concentrated was counted over a long time to obtain the reproducibility of the results; an average of 99.8% of bismuth activity was found to remain adsorbed (Table I). As regards the procedure by elution, the table shows that about 3% remains adhering to the glass powder. Further washing with HNO_3 does not improve the situation. But addition of a finite quantity of bismuth to HNO_3 , the remaining 3% can be eluted. If it is desirable to obtain whole of the carrier-free bismuth activity, our procedure under identical conditions requires the addition of 3% to the eluted product. If a quantitative separation of bismuth activity is the object, the elution with a finite quantity of bismuth provides cent per cent bismuth activity in the solution free of any lead. The procedure therefore allows a quantitative cent per cent adsorption and recovery.

In group C, separation of bismuth activity in tracer level in presence of increasing amounts lead, the table shows that lead does not in any way affect the procedure. On an average, 97% RaE was recovered. If we add to it about 3% (the amount always found adhering to the glass) as the correction involved in the elution, complete separation of RaE in presence of finite quantities of lead can be guaranteed. Though appreciable amounts of lead were added, only traces of lead were found in bismuth fractions, which was rather negligible for any physical measurement.

Evidently, cent per cent carrier-free bismuth activity can be separated from lead at a finite or a tracer level. The attainment of maximum radiochemical purity, when both lead and bismuth are at a tracer level, is still a problem. Special procedures were adopted for this purpose. RaE after elution was mixed with finite amounts of lead and bismuth and the bismuth was chemically separated from lead by precipitating as bismuth phosphate by boiling with metaphosphoric acid. Two such separations were made to remove traces of bismuth. To the lead fraction some bismuth was also added and kept in HNO_3 solution for 30-35 days for the growth of RaE from the traces of RaD. The amount of RaE, which is a measure of RaD remaining in all the samples, has been included in Table I (D series). The percentage of lead has been computed by making necessary corrections for the small amounts of lead which is lost in the separation procedure of bismuth from lead. RaE, thus separated, is of high radiochemical purity (99.8%).

The question naturally arises whether this type of procedure is successful in presence of finite quantities of bismuth and lead in classical chemistry. Preliminary observation shows that a certain amount of bismuth remains in solution probably due to the formation of an acetate complex anion of bismuth at finite concentrations. Even at a tracer level, adsorption on glass powder did not exceed 99.8%.

From the results recorded, the present method can be claimed to be simple in principle and operation, providing a quantitative separation and recovery of RaD and RaE with high radiochemical purity.

The question of time is also an important factor. The adsorption including washing takes about an hour. But subsequent elution of RaE will also take about an hour. So the final collection of RaE including measurements may be done in $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The product can be made free of solid matter by an easy operation. Thus the product of high radiochemical purity can be obtained by a simple method of forming a complex with one of the constituents.

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